

Proximate biochemical composition of seed *Ocimum gratissimum* (Wild Basil)

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Manuscript received online 22 May 2013, revised 05 July 2013, accepted 07 July 2013

Abstract : The proximate physicochemical properties and chemical composition of Wild Basil seeds, along with amino acid composition and content was investigated. The compositions of the fatty acids of the extracted oil were also determined. The proximate analysis of Wild Basil (*Ocimum gratissimum*) seeds showed the following composition : oil (9.69%), protein (9.58%), moisture (8.62%), ash (0.25%), total dietary fiber (39.82%) and total carbohydrates (71.58%). The fatty acid profile of the oil showed respectively three saturated fatty acids (C16 : 0, C18 : 0 and C20 : 0), one monounsaturated fatty acid (C18 : 1) and two polyunsaturated fatty acids (C18 : 2, C18 : 3). Linoleic acid (76.14%) was the major unsaturated fatty acid while palmitic acid was the main saturated one (8.53%). The amounts of amino acids were also determined by HPLC. The analysis of these characteristics showed interesting application potential for food industry.

Keywords : *Ocimum gratissimum*, biochemical properties, fatty acid profile, amino acid profile, total dietary fiber.

Introduction

The longstanding interest in finding new sources of food ingredients with high nutritional, industrial and pharmaceutical values leads to investigate new sources of food ingredients, especially among the non-conventional and unexploited sources. So, it has been observed that more and more attention is being paid to the use of by-products from food processing waste and underexploited forest products¹. Wild Basil (*Ocimum gratissimum*) is a member of genus *Ocimum*. The genus *Ocimum* comprises between 50 and 150 species of herbs and shrubs. Distributed worldwide, it is found in the tropical regions of Asia, Africa and Central and South America². Basil is one of the endemic plants in India that is produced and used as a pharmaceutical plant in high quantity. *Ocimum* is an erect, hairy, annual herb, found throughout India, up to an altitude of 1800 m in the Himalayas. In India; traditionally the seeds of *Ocimum gratissimum* (Locally known as Wild Basil) have been used in the treatment of dysentery and diarrhoea. These seeds are mucilaginous. Species belonging to the genus *Ocimum* L., Basil (Lamiaceae) are rich in essential oils which have been employed as a major character for selection and domesti-

cation of aromatic plants³. Vieira and Simon⁴ and Vieira *et al.*⁵ were profiled the essential oils found in *Ocimum* species. Furthermore, at least three essential oil chemotypes are known to be present in *Ocimum gratissimum*. In addition, it has also been reported that the seeds of *Ocimum sanctum* contain some anticoagulase factors⁶. One of the major components of the *Ocimum* sp. leaves is essential oil, eugenol, which may be assisting in exerting the hypoglycaemic and hypolipidemic effect⁷. Being a plant source *Ocimum gratissimum* is rich in fiber. According to the American Association of Cereal Chemists, dietary fiber consists of edible parts of plants or analogous carbohydrates can resist digestion and absorption in the small intestine, with complete or partial fermentation in the large intestine. Many epidemiological studies have provided evidence that consumption of fiber-rich foods may reduce risk of certain types of cancer, namely, colon, rectum and breast⁸⁻¹⁰. The influence of dietary fibers on blood lipids has been extensively documented in the last decades. Several studies showed that the lowering of cholesterol can be attributed to the intake of high soluble fiber¹¹. *Ocimum gratissimum* seed may not necessarily possess hypoglycemic and/or hypolipidemic

properties, thereby suggesting the need for studying the effect of various plant sources rich in fiber. It was reported that the genus *Ocimum* contains seed oils that are not only edible, but whose high ω -3 fatty acid content makes it suitable for use by the petroleum, paint, and varnish industries, and in the manufacture of printing inks and soaps, as with linseed oil¹².

There are many reports about the investigation of fatty acid variation of seed oil¹², extraction of gum¹³, study of essential oil of *Ocimum* leaf, but there is no published study of total biochemical composition of the seed especially for the total dietary fibre extracted from Basil seed and amino acid profiling of *Ocimum* sp. seed protein. In the present study the all major constituents of the seeds had been reported which may help in its potential application by food industries.

Results and discussion

The proximate composition of *Ocimum gratissimum* seed, fatty acid composition of the extracted oil of *Ocimum gratissimum*, proximate composition analysis of seed, fatty acid composition of extracted oil, amino acid profile, total, soluble and insoluble fiber contents are presented in the Tables 1–4 respectively.

The results of the proximate composition of the oil seed is presented in Table 1. The moisture content of the seed *O. gratissimum* was $8.62 \pm 0.74\%$. The crude protein content of the seed 9.58% was reported in the Table 1. The protein content of the seed (9.58%) seemed to be lower than the reported values of 16.4% for *O. basilicum*

and 24.2% for *O. americanum*, respectively²². But as per Mathews *et al.*¹³ protein content of the seed, *Ocimum basilicum* ranged 13.8% . The total oil content in the seed of the *O. gratissimum* was 9.69% . The oil content of this basil was lower than that found in many commercial oil plants such as rapeseed (*Brassica napus* 38 – 44%) or linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* 32 – 43%). Result on the total carbohydrate content was obtained as 71.58% . The seed contained significant amount of fibre which was 39.82% presented in Table 5. The total ash content of the seed was quite low and it was 0.25% .

The fatty acid composition of the oil is presented in Table 2. The carbon chain length found in the sample ranged from C_{16} to C_{20} including unsaturated fatty acids (i.e. $C_{18:1}$, $C_{18:2}$, $C_{18:3}$). The highest portion of unsaturated fatty acids averaged 87.25% , with the major fatty acids being linoleic acid (76.14%) and oleic acid (7.45%), along with lesser amounts of linolenic acid 3.7% . The most abundant saturated acids included palmitic acid (8.53%) and stearic acid (0.935%). This result emphasized important differences in the relative ratios of linoleic to linolenic acids in basil seed oils, and compared similarly to most literature values. Table 2 also contains the analytical values of the oil of Wild Basil. Iodine value and saponification value of the oil obtained was 138.96 and 206.31 respectively. This high iodine value indicates the presence of high amount of unsaturated fatty acid in the oil.

Table 3 presents the amino acid profile of the protein extracted from *Ocimum gratissimum* de-oiled cake. It is clearly noted that the protein of de-oiled cake of *Ocimum gratissimum* contains all the essential amino acids. So, the protein of the seed *Ocimum gratissimum* can be utilised to make further improvement in preparation of good nutritious protein. Fig. 1 shows the HPLC chromatogram of amino acid profile.

Table 4 depicts the total, soluble and insoluble fiber content of *Ocimum gratissimum* meal. The IDF value (35.43 ± 1.49) for the meal obtained from the seed was higher than the SDF value (3.6 ± 0.24).

Table 1. Proximate composition analysis of *Ocimum gratissimum* seeds

Proximate composition Parameter	Content (%)
Moisture	8.62 ± 0.74
Oil	9.69 ± 0.82
Protein	9.58 ± 0.63
Total carbohydrate	71.58 ± 2.3
Ash	0.25 ± 0.02

Table 2. Fatty acid composition and analytical characteristic of oil from *Ocimum gratissimum*

Fatty acid (% w/w) Sample	$C_{16:0}$	$C_{18:0}$	$C_{18:1}$	$C_{18:2}$	$C_{18:3}$	$C_{20:0}$	Iodine value	Saponification value
<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>	8.53 ± 0.8	0.935 ± 0.021	7.45 ± 1.23	76.14 ± 3.38	3.7 ± 0.41	2.43 ± 0.05	138.96 ± 9.41	206.31 ± 10.3

Table 3. Amino acid composition of the protein extracted from *Ocimum gratissimum* meal

Amino acids	Amount (% w/w of protein)
Aspartic acid	5.56 ± 0.12
Glutamic acid	11.09 ± 0.051
Serine	6.82 ± 0.13
Histidine	1.8 ± 0.11
Glycine	11.68 ± 0.036
Threonine	5.61 ± 0.08
Arginine	5.03 ± 0.015
Alanine	9.77 ± 0.07
Tyrosine	2.2 ± 0.14
Valine	2.83 ± 0.10
Methionine	0.67 ± 0.015
Cystein	1.67 ± 0.021
Isoleucin	1.96 ± 0.021
Leucin	5.86 ± 0.035
Phenylalanine	2.83 ± 0.025
Lysine	5.3 ± 0.015

Chemicals : TDF100A kit diethyl ethoxymethyl-enamalonate and standard L-aminoacid mixtures were purchased from Sigma Aldrich Co. (Bangalore, India). Phenol was obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). All other chemicals and solvents used were either of analytical or chromatographic grades.

Moisture content : Accurately weighed 10 g of sample into tared moisture dish. The sample was dried in the hot air oven at 110 ± 3 °C for 1.5 h according to AOCS method¹⁴, removed from the oven, covered immediately, cool in desiccators to room temperature and weigh. Sample kept in oven up to constant weight.

Moisture, % = loss in weight, g × 100/Weight of sample, g

Estimation of total oil content and preparation of de-oiled seed :

Oil content was determined upon extraction of the sample using *n*-hexane in a Soxhlet apparatus according

Table 4. Total, soluble and insoluble dietary fiber contents of *Ocimum gratissimum* meal

Variety	Total dietary fiber (%)	Soluble dietary fiber (%)	Insoluble dietary fiber (%)
<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>	39.82 ± 7.91	3.6 ± 0.24	35.43 ± 1.49

Fig. 1. HPLC analysis of amino acid of *Ocimum gratissimum* meal. Aspartic acid (peak 1); Glutamic acid (peak 2); Serine (peak 3); Histidine (peak 4); Glycine (peak 5); Threonine (peak 6); Arginine (peak 7); Alanine (peak 8); Tyrosine (peak 9); NH₃ (peak 10); Valine (peak 11); Methionine (peak 12); Cystein (peak 13); Isoleucine (peak 14); Leucine (peak 15); Phenylalanine (peak 16); Lysine (peak 17).

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Materials : Whole seeds of *Ocimum gratissimum* were purchased from Local market of Kolkata, West Bengal, India. Whole seed was grinded in a high-speed electric grinder and stored in an air tight container at 4 °C.

to AOCS method¹⁵ for about 24 h until negligible residual oil content and desolventised in vacuum and stored in air tight container at 4 °C for further analysis.

Estimation of iodine value and saponification value of oil of seed :

Iodine value and saponification value were measured

according to AOCS method¹⁶.

Estimation of total protein content :

Standard analytical techniques were used. Crude protein was determined by the Kjeldahl method and reported as $N \times 6.25$, according to AOCS method¹⁷. This factor was adopted, as it is the standard used by the food and feed industry.

Estimation of total carbohydrate content :

Total carbohydrate content was determined by modified phenol-sulphuric acid method¹⁸. In the sample solution 5% phenol solution was added and followed by 96% sulphuric acid. It was incubated at 25–30 °C for 20 min. Absorbance reading was taken at 490 nm against glucose as a standard curve by spectrophotometer (UV-Vis 1600, Shimadzu).

Estimation of total ash content :

Total ash content of the seeds were analysed according to AOCS method¹⁹.

Estimation of total, soluble and insoluble fiber :

The proximate analysis of total, soluble and insoluble dietary fiber of *Ocimum* seeds were determined using AOAC methods (Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International, 16th Edition, Volume II, Section 45.4.07, Method 985.29 (1997))²⁰. Data was represented in Table 4.

Estimation of amino acid profile and content :

Amino acids were determined by precolumen derivatisation with diethyl ethoxymethylenemalonate and reverse-phase high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC 2487, Waters, USA) with spectrophotometric determination at 280 nm²¹. It was shown in Table 3.

Estimation of fatty acid composition of extracted oil by gas chromatography :

Fatty acid compositions of Wild Basil oil were analyzed by gas chromatography. The oils were saponified with 0.5 M KOH and methylated with BF₃ in methanol. The gas chromatograph (Agilent 6890 N) was fitted with a DB-Wax capillary column (30 m × 0.32 mm × 0.25 μm) and a flame ionization detector. N₂, H₂ and airflow rate were maintained at 1, 30 and 300 ml/min, respectively. Inlet and detector temperatures were kept at 250 °C and the oven temperature was programmed to increase from 150 °C to 190 °C at a rate of 15 °C/min, then to

hold for 5 min, and then to increase to 230 °C at a rate of 4 °C/min, and then to hold at 10 min. The fatty acid compositions of the Wild Basil oils are shown in Table 2; the Wild Basil oil contained 76.14% of fatty acids as linoleic acid.

Data analysis and statistical procedures :

All sets of experiment were carried out in triplicate. All results were expressed as the mean value ± SD.

Conclusion

In summary, Wild Basil seed may no longer be considered an inert dietary substance nor can its functional importance be confined only to the gastrointestinal tract or antimicrobial property. Characterising its biochemical properties have contributed to a better understanding of the complexity of seed and the spectrum of physiological effects which may be evoked by this diverse group of compounds.

Acknowledgement

The financial support of University Grant Commission (UGC) is gratefully acknowledged by the authors.

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